

A "L" SHAPE BAND REJECTION FILTER

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Resumo – Wireless communication is essentially in our daily lives, this article aims to simulate the use of microstrip antennas, which are antennas whose function is based on radio and microwave communication. This antennas are applicable in various communication areas, from use in electronic devices, Wi-Fi to radars, having the purpose of emitting or receiving electromagnetic waves to facilitate wireless communication. Thus presenting the projection of the application of this antenna and demonstrating its functionality through simulators and other tools.

Palavras-chave: Microstrips; Antennas; Microwaves

INTRODUCTION

The microstrip antennas [1] process the majority of the world's data and tend to dominate the processing due to their low cost, compact structure, and quality in transmission. An antenna has the capability to transmit and receive electromagnetic waves, however, it can also receive unwanted waves, thereby distorting the information. The solution to such a problem is use filters that can reduce the interference from these unwanted waves.

Filters play a crucial role in antennas, and this article presents a geometric study of a band-reject filter simulated in software.

DEVELOPMENT

The simulations were conducted using the QUCS Studio software. The software provides a transmission line calculator, a tool used for impedance matching of a line connecting transmitter P1 to receiver P2. The aim was to achieve a 50 Ω line. Figure 1 displays the parameters used to obtain the line.

A modification was made to the line by creating a branching in an "L" shape, as depicted in Figure 2. In the simulation, two values were measured: $S[2,1]$, which relates to the transmitted signal, and $S[1,1]$, which represents return loss. These measurements were taken for frequency ranges from 0.1 GHz to 10 GHz, discretized into 1000 points.

Figure 1 - Parameters used in the line calculator

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the figure below, the simulated circuit is depicted, showing each transmission line. The MS16 and MS19 transmission lines were specifically

selected for the filter to operate at the desired frequency.

Figure 2 - "L"-shaped Filter

The circuit was designed with a commonly used impedance of 50 Ohms. To achieve this value, transmission lines with a width of 3mm were developed. The total length of the filter is 40mm.

To operate at the frequencies of 2.8 GHz and 5 GHz, it was necessary to modify the length of the MS16 line to 6 mm and the MS19 line to 1.8 mm. After these modifications, the assembly was done, and the circuit was simulated, resulting in the following outcome:

Figure 3 - Filter Behavior

As shown in Figure 3, the points where the frequencies intersect correspond to values of approximately 2.8 GHz and 5.1 GHz, which are the

lower and upper cutoff frequencies of the circuit, respectively. The filter has a rejection bandwidth of 3.9 GHz.

The MS16 and MS19 transmission lines are crucial to defining the filter's operating frequency range. For future work, the same circuit can be used with different parameters to obtain new lower and upper cutoff frequencies and rejection bandwidth results.

In this way, the conclusion of this band-reject filter was tangible, as shown in Figure 3, proving to be an easily fabricated filter and demonstrating the versatility of the MicroStrip Line, as it is possible to vary the passband region by changing the line's shape.

REFERENCES

- [1] Colaco, J., & Lohani, R. B. (2021). Design and Comparison of the effect of SRR Metamaterial on the performance of Microstrip Patch Antenna of various shapes at millimetre-wave band Useful for 5G enabled Internet of Things Applications. In Journal of Physics: Conference Series (Vol. 1921). IOP Publishing Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1921/1/012032>
- [2] Neto, A., Neto, A., Andrade, M., Silva, J., & Carvalho, J. (2018). Filtro rejeita-faixa compacto com reduzida região de transição para aplicação na faixa de 2,4 GHz. Sociedade Brasileira de Telecomunicacoes. <https://doi.org/10.14209/sbtr.2018.233>
- [3] SIMÕES, B. G. et al. DESENVOLVIMENTO DE UM FILTRO REJEITA FAIXA UTILIZANDO MICROLINHAS DE TRANSMISSÃO. Disponível em: <<https://zenodo.org/record/7857203>>.